

THE IMPACT OF THE VALUE CREATION MODEL ON INVESTING IN THE INTELLECTUAL CAPITAL OF THE ENTERPRISE

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Abstract. In modern management theory, intellectual capital is regarded as one of the key sources of a company's competitive advantage; it includes formalized knowledge and human capital that form the consumer value of companies in the long term. The authors of this article investigate a significant factor that determines the strategy of investing in intellectual capital in order to support effective management decisions - this is a value creation model. Theoretical analysis has shown that the organization's value creation model can have a significant impact on the processes of attracting financial and organizational resources to intellectual capital, defining supporting, transforming or network strategies. Management practitioners can use the results when planning investment programs and analyzing promising areas for investing financial resources.

Key words: intellectual capital, investment, value creation model, theory.

Introduction

In the last two decades, researchers have noted the extraordinary interest of managers of companies in various fields of activity in the problems of intellectual capital management [1]; almost every company has ever thought about the presence of hidden resources, which consist in employees, internal databases or customer relationships that can increase the likelihood for the company to become more productive in the long term. The management of such resources requires certain

knowledge from managers, in particular, competencies in the field of investment analysis of intellectual resources remain rare, which focus on investments in employee training, formalization of knowledge management processes and building sustainable relationships with customers that would form the company's reputation capital. An urgent task, therefore, is not only the competent identification of intellectual resources of companies, but also the definition of rational approaches to the organization and evaluation of the economic efficiency of investment projects in the field of research and development, organization of training and management of the company's image. The development of such strategies, in turn, is impossible without an unambiguous understanding of the full range of factors that influence the investment behavior of companies managers need to understand and explain what determinants can determine the success of investment projects that require significant financial resources.

The development of the theory of intellectual capital is currently faced with significant difficulties associated with the abundance of theoretical concepts, the applicability of which in practice often does not bring the desired results [2]. In this regard, the research program in the field of intellectual capital, announced in leading international publications on this topic, has been adjusted to achieve the best results in increasing the practical significance of works aimed at planning, coordinating and organizing intellectual resources of commercial companies and public sector organizations [3]. Meanwhile, the development of any practical recommendations should be based on rational assumptions, which are confirmed by the experience of the considered set of companies, in order to develop such rational models, it is necessary to turn to fundamental variables of organizational activity, such as factors of competitiveness, business modeling and investment activity. In particular, we

believe that the field of investment analysis is of considerable interest to practitioners, which determines the behavior of companies when investing financial and organizational resources in research and development, employee training and reputation management of the company. This article, based on the analysis of the literature, determines the impact on investment strategies of one of the key variables of an organization – a value creation model reflecting the logic of transforming resources in a company to create a competitive product or service.

1. INVESTMENTS IN INTELLECTUAL CAPITAL UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF VARIOUS ORGANIZATIONAL VARIABLES Before directly analyzing the factors that determine the long-term investment behavior of companies, it is necessary to refer to a preliminary note on the areas of investment. On the one hand, there are internal investments in intellectual capital – companies can use their own or borrowed funds to support projects to improve the infrastructure for information exchange, the formation of patent portfolios, the formation of ethical competencies among employees, etc. [4]. Thus, the sphere of internal investments is directly influenced by the views of managers and the accepted model of value creation. On the other hand, a company can act as an investment object (for example, through securities). In this case, the company needs to position its internal intellectual resources to attract the attention of potential and current investors to its activities in order to form a stable financial flow of funds [5]. In the study of factors, we will consider these areas in aggregate, determining their relationship under the influence of changes in consumer value creation models. From this point of view, external investments are the highest priority and sufficiently studied, since companies strive to make the internal environment sufficiently transparent for decision-making, disclosing elements in reporting, etc. (Fig. 1). N. ModSaleh et al.

(2013) pay attention to the sphere of external investments, they determine that investment decisions are influenced by the structure of intellectual capital (the ratio and quality of human, relational and structural capital) [4]. Structural capital has greater transparency, since it is tied to physical forms (licenses, trademarks recognized at fair value) and can be subjected to minimal distortion, and therefore attracts the close attention of potential investors. Among other factors, the authors name the quality of disclosure of intellectual capital and the experience of investors. S. Jorgenson et al. (2006) emphasize the importance of information asymmetry when making strategic decisions on investing in intellectual resources [6]. O. Letyushenkova and I. Lapina (2014) note that investments in intellectual capital may differ under the influence of the intended purpose: some of them are aimed at creating, another at supporting, and the third at developing existing intellectual resources [7]. For example, the support of communication and control systems provides value for internal consumers, investment decisions are made depending on the depth of projects and the nature of intellectual capital management processes (creation of a new resource, support of the current state or development). Significant influence in the field of external investments is given to information disclosure processes, for example, in the Mkumbuzi (2016) in the course of the study reveals that companies that are able to maintain adequate management systems due to the separation of executive and non-executive responsibilities and, to a lesser extent, due to the presence of experienced non-executive directors, demonstrate a higher level of disclosure of information about intellectual capital [5]. Also, a high level of liquidity of companies, a low level of borrowed funds are also associated with a high level of disclosure of intellectual capital and investment attractiveness associated with these factors. All the factors considered relate to various private characteristics

of companies, meanwhile, it is necessary to pay attention to system-forming factors, such as business models and value creation models in companies, which are directly related to the competitiveness of companies and consumer value creation models.

2. VALUE CREATION MODELS AS AN INVESTMENT FACTOR FOR INTELLECTUAL CAPITAL Value creation models are used in the study of strategically important types of activities in a company that can reveal the logic of creating consumer success of goods or services [8]. In our opinion, the analysis of the factors of investment behavior of companies should begin with the analysis of such models, since they relate to the most basic organizational variables that determine the logic of the functioning of the enterprise. It is known that there are at least three stable models of value creation – chain, workshop and network [9]. Value chains have been known in practice for the longest time, its purpose is to transform incoming resources into finished products or services that can be implemented at the next stage of consumption. Such chains are characterized by consistency, standardization of production and management business processes to support maximum returns from increasing the scale of activities. An example of such chains can be traditional industrial enterprises. Value shops never create a standardized product or service at the output, this type of value model is problem-oriented – it is aimed at solving the unique tasks of the company's customers [9]. Companies use intensive value creation models in order to offer customers unique solutions that are acceptable for their business conditions, an example of such companies can be consulting firms. However, they use the general knowledge and skills of employees, which can be a kind of analogue of standards for solving problems, despite the fact that the final solution is always unique. Value networks are designed to connect stakeholders (for example, buyers and sellers) within a single infrastructure. The

purpose of such companies is to develop their interaction network to increase the efficiency of its work and attract new users, examples are Internet aggregators of digital commerce. The nature of the activities of companies using different value models, thus, creates diversity in the investment functions of companies - imposes restrictions and creates opportunities for the processes of planning, analysis, attraction, organization, control and evaluation of the effectiveness of investments, depending on the organizational context. At the theoretical level, we believe that enterprises using value chains use intellectual resources to maintain basic business processes. Naturally, technology can play a key role in competitiveness. However, its operation can be permanent, systematic and even standardized. Thus, the company can only support its functions by attracting moderate investments in renewal, but significant investments for infrastructure modernization. Such companies really focus not on constant cycles of innovative modernization, but on the exploitation of relatively stable intellectual resources that bring returns for a long time. The material side of the production process, therefore, plays a fundamental role in ensuring the long-term success of the company along with the "standard" intellectual resources. External investments of companies are determined by the attractiveness of resource bases (for example, minerals, cheap labor, etc.), and internal investments are determined by the desire to maintain a level of technology acceptable for the operation of such resource bases. An example of companies supporting such strategies of investing in intellectual capital are metallurgical companies. Investments in intellectual capital are often designed to ensure limited development of technologies, human capital and customer image, since companies do not plan to receive significant returns from their operation. Companies applying value workshop models use relatively stable intellectual resources (human and

structural capital), which also need to be updated, in addition, their feature is the constant transformation of human capital into structural and relational, thus, investments in intellectual capital have a transformative role. Such companies transform intellectual resources, which acquire a different form, configuration necessary to solve unique customer tasks, they benefit from such a transformation. Consequently, such companies pay more attention to investment processes and take an active position in attracting financial and organizational resources. Network companies apply special network strategies for investing in human capital, they support infrastructure elements, in which intellectual resources play a key role, supporting consumer interaction to create value. Such companies invest heavily in maintaining the image of their communication platforms and facilities. Such companies attract long-term investments to maintain a communication network, relational capital plays a key role for them, while it is important for these companies to maintain the continuity of investment processes.

CONCLUSION

Intellectual capital is currently an important area of research from the standpoint of management theory. The study of the factors determining investment strategies is one of the key areas for understanding the processes of transformation of intellectual resources – their creation, transformation and support. This article shows the influence of value creation models, as a fundamental characteristic of organizational processes in a company from a strategic perspective, on the processes of investing in intellectual capital. Companies, depending on the value creation model, can apply supportive, transformative or network strategies for investing in intellectual capital. The results of the work can be used to develop investment decisions in companies

of various profiles to systematize the processes of attracting financial and organizational resources in the field of intellectual capital.

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